

http://plugin35.marketingdigitaltools.com/

NOVO TESTE

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1 <!doctype html>
2 <html lang="pt-PT" prefix="og: http://ogp.me/ns#">
3
4 <head>
5 <title>Marketing Digital Tools - Agência de Marketing Digital
6 <!-- WooCommerce SEO Plugin 1.3.002 -->
7 <meta name="description" content="- Marketing Digital Tools" /
8 <link rel="canonical" href="http://plugin35.marketingdigitalto
9 <meta property="og:url" content="http://plugin35.marketingdigi
10 <meta property="og:title" content="Marketing Digital Tools -
11 <meta property="og:description" content="- Marketing Digital
12 <meta property="og:type" content="website" />
13 <meta property="og:image" content="http://plugin35.marketingdi
14 <meta property="og:image:width" content="500" />
15 <meta property="og:site_name" content="Marketing Digital Tools
16 <meta property="og:locale" content="pt_PT" />
17 <meta property="twitter:url" content="http://plugin35.marketing
18 <meta property="twitter:title" content="Marketing Digital Tool
19 <meta property="twitter:description" content="- Marketing Digi
20 <meta property="twitter:image" content="http://plugin35.mark
21 <meta property="twitter:domain" content="Marketing Digital Toc
22 <meta property="twitter:card" content="summary" />
23 <meta name="google-site-verification" content="sQBJ98u1EC3V5-8
24 <script>(function(i,s,o,g,r,a,m){if('GoogleAnalyticsObject')=r;
25 <script>!function(f,b,e,v,n,t,s){if(f.fbq)return;n=f.fbq=funct
26 <script type="application/ld+json">{"@context":"http://\schem
27 <!-- /WooCommerce SEO Plugin -->
28 <meta charset="UTF-8">
29 <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, in
30 <link rel="profile" href="http://gmpg.org/xfn/11">
31
32
33 <link rel='dns-prefetch' href='//s.w.org' />
34 <link rel="alternate" type="application/rss+xml" title="Market
35 <link rel="alternate" type="application/rss+xml" title="Market
36 <script type="text/javascript">
37 window._wpemojiSettings = {"baseUrl":"https://\s.
38 !function(e,a,t){var r,n,o,i,p=a.createElement("c
39 </script>
40 <style type="text/css">
41 img.wp-smiley,
42 img.emoji {
43 display: inline !important;
44 border: none !important;
45 box-shadow: none !important;
46 height: 1em !important;
47 width: 1em !important;
48 margin: 0 .07em !important;
49 vertical-align: -0.1em !important;
50 background: none !important;
51 padding: 0 !important;
52 }
53 </style>
54 <link rel='stylesheet' id='wp-block-library-css' href='ht
55 <link rel='stylesheet' id='wc-block-style-css' href='http://p
56 <link rel='stylesheet' id='dashicons-css' href='http://plugi
57 <link rel='stylesheet' id='everest-forms-general-css' href='f
58 <link rel='stylesheet' id='woocommerce-layout-css' href='http
59 <link rel='stylesheet' id='woocommerce-general-css' href='htt
60 <link rel='stylesheet' id='woocommerce-small-screen-css' href='htt
61 <style id='woocommerce-inline-inline-css' type='text/css'>
62 .woocommerce form .form-row .required { visibility: visible; }
63 </style>
64 <link rel='stylesheet' id='font-awesome-css' href='http://pl
65 <link rel='stylesheet' id='zakra-style-css' href='http://plug
66 <style id='zakra-style-inline-css' type='text/css'>

```

Organization

All (1)

Organization	PRÉ-ERROS	0 AVISOS
ID: http://plugin35.marketingdigitaltools.com/		
@type	Organization	
@id	http://plugin35.marketingdigitaltools.com/	
url	http://plugin35.marketingdigitaltools.com/	
name	Marketing Digital Tools	
telephone	+351913824934	
description	Agência de Marketing Digital Ecommerce	
sameAs	https://www.facebook.com/marketingdigitaltools/	
sameAs	https://twitter.com/mktdigitaltools	
sameAs	https://www.instagram.com/marketingdigitaltools	
sameAs	https://www.linkedin.com/company/34891093/admin/	
sameAs	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCpRZ4JVRJFdvCmQ06i5zFiw/featured	
logo		
@type	ImageObject	
url	http://plugin35.marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/Logo-MDT-FINAL-III.png	
contactPoint		
@type	ContactPoint	
telephone	+351913824934	
potentialAction		
@type	SearchAction	
target		
@type	EntryPoint	
urlTemplate	http://plugin35.marketingdigitaltools.com?s={search_string}	
query-input		
@type	PropertyValueSpecification	
valueRequired	http://schema.org/True	
valueName	search_string	